

Hunting for *Ericas* in Madagascar

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Erica is a very large and widespread genus with some 860 species in a north-south distribution ranging from Lapland in the north to the Cape of Good Hope in the south. To help us understand the evolution of the genus and to help with its subdivision and the relationships of species over the whole range, a team at Stellenbosch University is undertaking an analysis of the DNA of a large sample of species, presently 480 and hopefully up to 650. We have samples from many areas in the distribution range including European species, but one area that was almost entirely lacking was Madagascar. The team consists of Dr Mike Pirie, a young postdoctoral researcher from UK, Professor Dirk Bellstedt and myself.

Madagascar is currently known to have about 45 species of *Erica* and all of them were formerly in the separate genus *Philippia*. All of them are endemic: in other words they occur only on the island. The last revision of the Malagasy species was produced by Perrier de la Bathie in 1927. Since then more material has been collected and more areas have been investigated. Dr Larry Dorr who set up the offices of Missouri Botanical Garden in Madagascar in the 1980s started looking at the genus there and finds that quite a few more species need to be described, but with lots of research required to resolve all the variation in and between the species.

In April 2010 the Nineteenth International Congress on African Plants was held in the capital, Antananarivo. We used the opportunity of attending the conference to put in some field work before and afterwards in order to find and collect some of these *Erica* species. Much planning had to go into the expedition since none of us had been to the island before and the bureaucratic setup was the usual problem for an African country. Fortunately Larry came to the congress and managed to join us for the trip down south to revitalize his interest in the genus. Apart from his experience with Malagasy species of *Erica*, his knowledge of French and Malagache came in very handy.

The British were the first colonial power on the island and therefore many of the early plant collections by colonial officials and missionaries from the London Missionary Society were sent to the Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew, where they were described in the mid- to later 1800s. Later in the nineteenth century the French took over the island in an 'exchange' and the subsequent collections landed up in Paris with many of them still to be worked through.

The species of *Erica* occur mainly along the highland plateau that runs down the centre of the island for some thousand kilometres, at an average altitude of 1,100m. Along this plateau there are numbers of small outcropping peaks and some larger ranges which attracted our attention after checking the localities

Figure 1. Andringitra National Park with two *Erica* species in the foreground and two large waterfalls (Riambavy, the queen, and Riandahy, the king) in the background.

Figure 2. Mike Pirie investigating a tall *Erica* with two other smaller species nearby.

Figure 3. On the way up to Pic Boby through large granite boulders and dense stands of heaths.

of all the collections listed by Larry. The large, southern mountains of the Ampidianombilahy Range fall mainly in the Andringitra National Park and this was our first objective (Figure 1). The 450km drive to Andringitra along a narrow, windy / winding, national road gave us our first glimpse of heathers growing on grassy hillsides with scattered eucalypts, pines and wattles, all weedy aliens of course. At one point we had to stop because of a very recent motorcar accident. This allowed me a quick visit to the nearby roadside slope which revealed five species of *Erica* in a hundred square metres! This is certainly the highest species diversity outside of the Cape.

We spent four days in Andringitra National Park camping on a mid-altitude plateau at about 2,000m. Hiking in the park is relatively easy with over 100km of trekking routes which are becoming popular destinations for outdoor enthusiasts visiting the island during the winter months. The park is closed during the rainy summer months due to impassable access routes. Guides have to be employed and porters are eager to take one's heavy packs and tents, and our plant presses, up to the campsite. They also do all the cooking which consists of rice and more rice with some other food admixed – all supplied by ourselves for everyone! Fortunately the weather was perfect for the four days and this allowed us to hike around with light day-packs to study the flowering and fruiting heaths easily.

Figure 4. View of Ampidianombilahy Mountains from the summit of Pic Boby with numerous *Erica* species in all the vegetated places.

Figure 5. Andringitra, mid-altitude plateau (2,000m) with two species on the shallow soiled flats: low, dark green *Erica rakotozafyana* and the reddish brown mass of *E. madagascariensis* (see Figure 10) in a boggy area in the middle distance. Note the dense olive-green covering of heaths on slopes on the left.

Figure 6 (both). *Erica baroniana*.

Figure 7. *Erica boutonii*.

The mountains are composed of impressive granite outcrops (Figures 1, 2 and 4). The central area has the second highest peak in Madagascar, Pic Boby (Imarivolanitra in Malagache) (altitude 2,658m). We easily got to the summit and had an amazing view of the range to the north (Figure 4). Apart from the forests in ravines and on sheltered moist slopes the open slopes are dominated by *Erica* species to the extent that they can sometimes form an impenetrable subforest with trees growing to 6m tall (Figure 1). Mostly they are 1–2m tall forming an olive-green ‘carpet’ over the slopes and in every gully (Figures 2, 3 and 4). Where there are shallow soils or boggy areas the heaths are small, low shrublets (Figure 5). There is no shortage of water in the park with many gushing streams (Figure 1), but despite this the vegetation is

Figure 8 (both). *Erica goudotian*, very like *E. scoparia* from south-west Europe.

sometimes set alight by lightning strikes or nowadays by indiscriminate human burning practices. It would appear that only a few of the species are resprouters so burning could have a serious effect on the survival of the smaller, more delicate and rarer species.

The Madagascar species all bear rather small, dull-coloured flowers with a large dish-like stigma like a satellite dish (Figures 6–10). Some of the flowers are attractively coloured (Figure 10), at least when looked at from close-up. They are generally believed to be wind-pollinated although several, with their remarkably altered stigmas (Figures 11 and 12), could well have another pollination syndrome. When disturbed these species did not release clouds of pollen like the others. Quite a number of the species looked very similar to the philippioid and salaxid species from the Cape or to *Erica scoparia* from Europe (Figure 8). For me it was amazing to see some species growing low among restiad reeds in a seepage zone exactly like our species do in the Cape and like the heathers growing on the Roundstone Bog in Connemara, Ireland.

During the Congress we went separately on different one-day excursions for delegates and I managed to pick up a few heathers in the Tapia woodlands west of Antananarivo. After the Congress we visited the Ankaratra Range around a hundred kilometres south of the capital. Unfortunately, clouds kept us from reaching the interesting summit ridges of Tsiafajavona (altitude 2,643m), but we

Figure 9 (above). *Erica bojeri*, sometimes with yellowish flowers and red stigma.
Figure 10 (right). Unidentified species of *Erica*.

Figure 11 (left). *Erica madagascariensis* (see Figure 5).
Figure 12 (above). *Erica parkeri*.

did see some interesting and different species of *Erica*, one of which with its open leaves and amazing stigmas appears to be a new species. Access to the mountain was by old gravel roads built by the French forestry authorities ages ago but not maintained since they had to leave the island in the early 1970s. Some of these roads were difficult to negotiate even on foot!

With all the hype about conservation in Madagascar we had to go through the strict bureaucratic procedures for allowing us to collect and to export our material. We appear to have collected about 26 species with several of them difficult to identify and possibly as yet undescribed.

Madagascar is a wonderful place to visit now that it is being opened up to outsiders. Tourism is picking up slightly after the political unrest in 2009, but tourists are mainly heading for the fine beach resorts and reserves along the east and north coasts. Few 'dare' to tackle the interior where there are good trekking possibilities and places to experience island life in the many villages and towns that the main roads pass through. The most striking thing about the island is, alas, the destruction to the environment that has already happened and, alas, is still occurring at a rapid rate – forest and grassland degradation, overgrazing and bad ploughing practices, and the inexorable spread of alien trees (eucalypts, pines and wattles). All available valleys and wet slopes have been ploughed up for paddy fields so this natural habitat is very rare. With the high rainfall in the central highlands all the large rivers roaring down to the east and west coasts are full of red mud and silt which pour out into the sea – Madagascar certainly lives up its name of the Red Island.